

Studies on *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]-2-hydroxy-1-aminoethane complexes of cobalt-, nickel- and copper(II)

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Complexes of the types ML_2 and ML_2Cl_2 [where M is Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , and L is the Schiff base (formed by condensation of 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde and 2-ethanolamine) *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]-2-hydroxy-1-aminoethane (TNAHE)] have been prepared. The results suggest a distorted octahedral geometry for the ML_2 and CoL_2Cl_2 complexes and a square-planar one for the ML_2Cl_2 complexes (M = Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}). The central metal atom coordinates through N and S atoms in the ML_2Cl_2 complexes and through N, S and O atoms in the ML_2 compounds.

In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the results of our studies on the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of Schiff base [derived from 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde (2-TFCA) and 2-ethanolamine (2-EA)] *N*-[thienylmethylidene]-2-hydroxy-1-aminoethane (TNAHE).

Results and discussion

The Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} complexes with *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]-2-hydroxy-1-aminoethane (TNAHE) are insoluble in methanol, ethanol and ethyl ether but soluble in DMF and DMSO. On the basis of the elemental analysis, the ML_2 and ML_2Cl_2 stoichiometries have been suggested for the compounds (Table 1).

IR and NMR spectra :

The band appearing in the spectrum of the ligand at 1645 cm^{-1} ($C=N$ of the azomethine group) shifts towards lower frequencies ($\Delta\nu = 20\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. This suggests that TNAHE is coordinated to the central metal ion through the azomethine nitrogen. The ligand band at 870 cm^{-1} ($C-S-C$)² is shifted by $30\text{--}50\text{ cm}^{-1}$ towards lower

Table 1. Physical data for the complexes

Compd.	M.p. °C	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$
$Co(TNAHE)_2$	180	Red	5.2	9.5
$Ni(TNAHE)_2$	240	Yellow	3.1	5.2
$Cu(TNAHE)_2$	230	Yellow	1.96	9.7
$Co(TNAHE)_2Cl_2$	250	Pink	4.9	15.2
$Ni(TNAHE)_2Cl_2$	190	Brown	Diamag.	119.8
$Cu(TNAHE)_2Cl_2$	220	Brown	1.8	113.5

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, S, N and Cl (last three compds.) analysis.

wavenumbers in the complexes, suggesting the involvement of sulfur atom in the bonding with the metal ions. The ligand band at 630 cm^{-1} , assigned to the $\nu_{C-S\text{ asym}}$ vibration, is similarly shifted in the complexes; the $\nu_{C-S\text{ sym}}$ band (from 685 cm^{-1}) completely disappears after coordination. This also confirms that the sulfur atom of the thiophene ring is a donor atom³.

IR spectrum of the ligand reveals a band at 1140 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the $C-OH$ group. In the spectra of the ML_2Cl_2 compounds this band appears at $1133\text{--}1142\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but in the case of ML_2 it is shifted towards lower side by $40\text{--}60\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Also, the band appearing for the free ligand at 3550 cm^{-1} (OH) disappears in the spectra of the ML_2 com-

plexes indicating the deprotonation of the OH group, while in the spectra of the ML_2Cl_2 it does not show a marked shift. On the basis of these data, it can be concluded that in the ML_2 compounds the ligand coordinates through the oxygen atom. The proof of the coordination through the O and N atoms is provided by the occurrence of the bands at $460\text{--}478\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of the ML_2 complexes and at $417\text{--}430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the compounds.

From the IR spectral studies, it is obvious that the ligand acts as tridentate in the ML_2 complexes, coordinating through azomethine N, hydroxyl O and thiophene S, while in the ML_2Cl_2 complexes, it acts as bidentate, coordinating through azomethine N and thiophene S.

In the 1H NMR spectrum of the ligand, the 5-H proton of the thiophene ring appears at δ_2 7.3 and the azomethine proton ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) at δ_1 8.9 ppm⁴. The OH proton gives a signal at δ_3 4.7 ppm. In spectrum of the NiL_2Cl_2 complex the signals δ_1 and δ_2 shift downfield by 0.3–1 ppm. These observations support the bonding of TNAHE through nitrogen and sulfur atoms.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra provide further support for the coordination mode of TNAHE. In the spectra of the complexes, the signals due to azomethine carbon, 2-C and 5-C (thiophene ring) show a distinct downfield shift by nearly 2.5–6 ppm, clearly demonstrating the coordination of the ligand through the nitrogen and the sulfur atoms.

Electronic and ESR spectra :

The electronic spectrum of the ligand exhibits three intense bands at 41518 ($\epsilon=7300$), 37340 (6500) and 32560 cm^{-1} (3000). The band at 41518 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the thiophene ring and the remaining two bands to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the chromophore C=N. These bands are also observed in the spectra of the complexes, but they are shifted towards the lower frequencies ($\Delta\nu = 1500\text{--}2200\text{ cm}^{-1}$), confirming the coordination of the ligand to the metal ions.

The reflectance spectrum of Co(TNAHE)_2 consists of three bands at 9479, 16390 and 20620 cm^{-1} . For octahedral Co^{II} complexes three bands are expected, which correspond to the three spin-allowed transitions $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$ (ν_2) and $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). However, it has been pointed out⁵ that the transition $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ corresponds to a two-electrons jump and it will have much lower oscillator strength than the other two bands and will be much weaker. The band at 9479 cm^{-1} can therefore be assigned to the ν_1 transition and the band at 20620 cm^{-1} to the ν_3 transition. Using the equations derived from the energy matrix of the two $^4T_{1g}$ levels⁶, the values of D_q and B calculated from the position of the ν_1 and ν_3 bands are 1069

and 823 cm^{-1} , respectively. Using the relationship $\nu_2 = \nu_1 + 10D_q$, the ν_2 band is expected to occur at about 20100 cm^{-1} , very close to the ν_3 band. The calculation suggests that the shoulder at 16390 cm^{-1} is not due to the ν_2 transition and is likely to be the spin-forbidden $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}(G)$ transition. The reflectance spectrum clearly indicates the compound to be octahedral, and this is supported by the magnetic moment, which lies in the range normally observed for Co^{II} octahedral complexes.

The reflectance spectrum of Co(TNAPY)_2Cl_2 exhibits five bands. By analogy with the assignments of Ferguson⁷, the bands at 18850 and 18120 cm^{-1} arise from the $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition, which is split in complexes of D_{4h} symmetry. The band observed at 15750 cm^{-1} arises from the $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}$ transition and those at 9400 and 8509 cm^{-1} from the $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$ transition.

For octahedral Ni^{II} complexes, three transitions are expected : $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). In the spectrum of Ni(TNAHE)_2 , the spin-allowed transition of the lowest energy (ν_1 , with a maximum at 9986 cm^{-1}) may be assigned to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$. The second band, observed near 14840 cm^{-1} , can be assigned to the ν_2 transition, while the highest energy transition, observed at 23018 cm^{-1} may be probably due to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$. This complex exhibits magnetic moment in the range expected for octahedral geometry. The complex Ni(TNAHE)_2Cl_2 is diamagnetic, suggesting an essentially square-planar environment for Ni^{II} , which is also supported by the bands at 21540 and 18010 cm^{-1} , assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively, in a planar arrangement of the ligand molecules around the Ni^{II} atoms⁸.

The electronic spectrum of Cu(TNAHE)_2 shows only one broad band at 16280 cm^{-1} , indicating probably a distorted octahedral geometry. The magnetic moment is 1.96 B.M. The ESR spectrum for this compound, measured in polycrystalline sample at room temperature, gives the following values : $g_{\parallel} = 2.032$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.216$. The value $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp}$ is well consistent with a primarily d_{z^2} ground state and the spectrum is characteristic for axial (compressed octahedral) symmetry⁹.

The electronic spectrum of Cu(TNAHE)_2Cl_2 shows absorption bands at 15210 and 18140 cm^{-1} , assignable to $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, supporting square-planar geometry¹⁰. The ESR spectrum recorded on the powdered sample revealed two g -values ($g_{\parallel} = 2.198$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.070$). The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ showed that the electron is delocalized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the ground state of Cu^{II} and the spectrum is characteristic for axial sym-

metry. The parameter G , determined as $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, is found to be much less than 4, suggesting a considerable interaction in the solid state¹¹.

The values of the molar conductance of the complexes, in DMF ($10^{-3}M$) solution, are in the range 113.5–119.8 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating their 1 : 2 electrolytic natures, except the ML_2 and CoL_2Cl_2 complexes, which are non-electrolytes.

Experimental

$CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck, 99.99%), $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck, 99.99%), $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Merck, 99.99%), 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde (Merck, 98%), 2-ethanolamine (Merck, 98%) were used.

Schiff base : An ethanolic solution of 2-TFCA (0.002 mol, 25 ml) was added to an ethanolic solution of 2-EA (0.002 mol, 25 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 8 h on a water-bath. The solution was then concentrated and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried over $CaCl_2$ in vacuum.

ML_2 complexes : An ethanolic solution of the corresponding metal chloride (0.002 mol, 50 ml) was added to an ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.004 mol, 50 ml), at pH 9.5–10.0. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2–4 h. The separated solid compounds were washed with ethanol and dried over $CaCl_2$ in vacuum (yields 60–77%).

ML_2Cl_2 complexes : A mixture of 2-TFCA (0.004 mol, 50 ml) and 2-EA (0.004 mol, 50 ml) in ethanol was added to an ethanolic solution of the corresponding metal chloride (0.002 mol, 50 ml), at pH = 7.5–8.0. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 6–8 h. The excess of solvent was then distilled. The separated solid compounds were washed

with ethanol and dried over $CaCl_2$ in vacuum (yields 58–84%).

Metals, S and Cl were analyzed by conventional methods, while C and N by microanalytical methods. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman DK2A spectrophotometer fitted with a standard reflectance attachment. 1H NMR spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian T60 spectrometer, ^{13}C NMR spectra on a Bruker WH 270 spectrometer and ESR spectra on an ART 5 spectrometer at room temperature. Magnetic moment was determined by the Faraday method. A K 612 conductivity meter was used to measure the molar conductivities in DMF solution.

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